

A TEACHER IS A LEADER OF THE COMMUNITY - A GUIDE STAR

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of a teacher in society, human qualities, the image of a modern teacher and his characteristics, and at the same time, the views of sages and scientists who lived in different periods about pedagogues can be observed in the history of many peoples of the world. is considered a guiding star. No society has matured without a teacher. That's why there are sayings in our nation: "The teacher is as great as your father." The meaning of the word "teacher" is broad. Whatever is happening in this enlightened world, the teacher is the fruit of discipleship. We learn something from neighbours, friends, family, books, press, nature, and sometimes from children. That's why education is a holy place that spreads knowledge. Education means to make people interested. Whoever wants to teach something to a child should first make him interested. Success in education will be a constant companion of a person who is interested. The teaching profession also means to stand in the middle and demonstrate skills throughout life. They should learn the secrets of public speaking in-depth and go on to study their chosen subjects. The teacher's knowledge is his property.*

Thousands of years ago, the great thinker Mahmud Kashgari wrote in his book "Devoni Lugotit Turk" about the issues of education, and morals, and said, "Time has completely decreased, knowledge, wisdom, and purity have decreased, evil people have increased, and the owners of virtue are disappearing." However, according to the development of time and society, new problems have arisen in the issue of youth education, and the tasks before educators and teachers have increased. People are not divided into good or bad as a whole. If it were so, the issue of upbringing would be easily solved. The struggle between good qualities and bad habits, different ideas to occupy the heart and mind of a person shows how complicated the issue of upbringing is.

Abdulla Avloni, when approaching the treatise "Turkish Gulistan or Morality", divides it into physical, intellectual and moral types and pays special attention to moral education.

Keywords: *teacher, teacher, ethics, virtue, education, image, people, human, education, child, writing, stress, beauty, law.*

INTRODUCTION

The main goal of all the good works carried out in our country is to increase the potential of our country, to ensure the well-being of our people, to strengthen the foundations of a free and prosperous Motherland, and to raise a perfect generation. large-scale reforms are being carried out, and the necessary conditions are being created. At a time when our country is constantly worrying about the prospects of our children, it is important to protect our youth from any foreign influences that undermine education and morale, to form a healthy immunity in our youth against the threat of information in the world, and to raise awareness. not to give - today it has become as important a necessity as water and air.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Boys and girls who grow up righteous from their youth will be kind to their parents and love their country and people, and kindness and love will have a strong place in their hearts.

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Imam Ghazali describes the qualities of righteous people in his book "O Child" and says:

"A child is like a beeswax. The coach can shape him into any shape he wants. A child is like a clean page next to his parents. No pattern or image has been placed in his heart. But such a soul is inclined to receive any pattern, that is, everything. That is why it is necessary to occupy it with good deeds. The child will grow into a perfect person if this soul is filled with virtues and knowledge."

The growth of such children guarantees that parents and teachers fully fulfil their responsibilities. To find one's way, and to have one's place - these are the main things for a person, it means his self-realization. In this, talents and abilities in a person are passed through genes. Therefore, women try to marry lucky men, and men want to marry beautiful and intelligent women. admires successful people and is inspired by their lives. When they grow up, other ideals are formed, new heroes appear, and young people aspire to them and imitate them. To be successful is to contribute to the well-being of the nation and the world, to improve life by creating positive changes, and to benefit society and people. means to bring. One of the factors that supports and strengthens the desire for success is imitation. People dream of being like the heroes they admire, and they have a desire to achieve high results in the field they are interested in. For this, they need an inspiring, imitating object. Every successful person has an inspiring image that they follow.

The great poet and scientist, the great representative of Persian-Tajik literature, Abdurakhman Jami, in his pedagogic views, calls upon the owners of the field to serve justice, politeness and wise words.

In different historical periods, unique methods and traditions have been formed to overcome the problems faced by education. The call to bravery and goodness on the inscriptions, the wisdom in the folklore, the virtues such as kindness, hard work, righteous kings, perfect children, virtuous people, and the moral teachings of the thinkers of the Middle Ages. we will witness the sources.

It is necessary to implement moral education in the pedagogical process, based on the requirements of continuity in the educational system, no matter how big and complicated it is.

Therefore, a general question arises: what should be the image of a modern teacher?

Nowadays, modern teachers demand to have the following characteristics.

1. The teacher should have aesthetic beauty

In the culture of dressing, for example, for male teachers, from a simple shirt to a well-groomed beard and hair is also important. There should be no room for distractions in this place. As Charles Darwin said, "Human nature always tries to exaggerate the beauty in itself."

2. The teacher must have a legal culture.

Today, some teachers do not know the articles of our Constitution on the equality of citizens, freedoms, rights and duties, and education.

Today's teacher must know perfectly not only our Constitution but also all the laws and regulations related to education. As a result of the low legal literacy of teachers, the cases involving the educators of the nation in forced labour or the corruption that bogs down the field are manifested.

The constitution and legislation can take a fair approach to the issue in a controversial situation with students or their parents and protect their rights on the spot. It is necessary to make changes to the legislation and become an active participant in social relations in society. For this, it is necessary to have a high level of legal culture. In Ibn Sina's pedagogical views, "an enlightened person should be brave, not afraid of death, and act only to find the truth". said that

3. He should know foreign languages other than his mother tongue.

First of all, the teacher must know the state language well, and then at least one foreign language. A well-known playwright, publicist, public figure, and one of the leaders of the Jadidist movement, Mahmudhoja Behbudi considered it necessary to know several languages for the development of the nation. He published Oyna magazine, a weekly magazine with pictures, mainly in Uzbek, poetry, articles (Persian), and announcements (Russian). The magazine will spread to the Caucasus, Tatarstan, Iran, Afghanistan, India, and Turkey. Behbudi will also publish a book. In the very first issue of the magazine, he published an article "Not two, but four languages are necessary". He considered it necessary to know Uzbek, Tajik, Arabic, Russian and even a foreign language (for example, French). At the same time, he has published important and necessary articles about the mutual relations of language protection. He paid great attention to literary criticism. Among modern enlightened intellectuals, they looked at the work of organizing education and school work and creating its foundations as a whole and achieved a lot of success in this way. These principles are reflected in the books and manuals they created for modern schools. Among modern enlightened pedagogues, the method created by Makhmudhuja Behbudi, Uzbek and Persian textbooks in the spirit of modernism became very popular in their time, and some of them were republished.

4. Must be aware of information technologies.

In today's era of globalization, the teacher should be aware of the events happening in his country and the world every day. and should make a scientific assessment of the relevant issue. Now, if we talk about the use of information media, the teacher needs to keep pace with the times and introduce innovations to education.

But technology is becoming very important in how we use information and even how we organize our lives. However, they should pay attention to the fact that the presence of something new and useful does not mean that the old method is no longer important. there are thoughts.

If we look at writing by hand from a psychological point of view, we will consider some useful aspects for a person:

Stress relief

Physical pain and mental torture are not alien to the person of today's violent times. The natural way to save from physical and mental torture is to fill a piece of white paper with one's inner thoughts. helps to improve.

Encourage creativity and thinking.

Due to personal and life problems, our imaginations and thoughts get confused. In quiet time, work is carried out with the features of the mind. It has been found that if every person makes writing a daily habit, it increases creativity deepens thinking, and develops brain activity.

Memory and recall.

We know that writing by hand is also scientifically proven to improve memory and recall. Moving the pen on the paper activates the brain, which helps people improve their cognitive abilities.

If a teacher respects himself, if he knows his values well, others will be forced to respect him. Every work is difficult, and the person doing it must be strong. A good teacher does not consider himself or his students to be inferior to anyone else in the world. A teacher pays attention to the special characteristics of children. Some children learn faster by hearing, and others by reading. When the goal is to improve the quality of humanity, whoever finds it easier to teach should be taught in this way.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the above opinions that we should remember the conclusions of one of the leaders of the Jadidist movement, Mahmudhoja Behbudi, who wrote in 1912. He expressed his thoughts as follows: "Secular science and knowledge are necessary to stand in the world. A nation that is deprived of modern science and science will be trampled on by others. In this advanced age, it is impossible to live without knowledge and enlightenment."

The sense of responsibility comes from the teacher's conscience. A student who sees so many qualities in a teacher looks at life through the eyes of his teacher and sees life not in black and white, but in grey colours and falls in love with it. He grows up to contribute to the beauty of this beautiful life and nation. He thinks that it will benefit the development of this society. This responsibility has a great place in the child's faith and morals, mind and social education.

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